

Paper: Why Do Users Struggle to Get Insights out of Process Mining?

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Supporting Materials

In this document we provide additional materials to section **3. Research Method and Data Collection**

This study was a part of a bigger research on trust and interpretability in process mining. In this document we share only parts that are relevant to this study and research question:

What are the factors influencing how PM consumers use PM output and get insights out of it?

1. Participants Selection

Inclusion criteria

The goal of this paper (and interviews) is to gain better understanding on how business users of a process mining (PM) solutions use the process mining analysis as process mining output (for example, set of dashboards in process mining solution) to get insights out of it. Therefore, **as our main selection criteria we focused on:**

- 1) Participants from industry/practice with a **business user** roles in process mining.
- 2) Participants with a **consumer** role activities. In case users combined both roles responsibilities, we asked them to focus on the consumer point of view. However, when user had more producer activities, we decided to not conduct interview with such a user.
- 3) Participants have to be involved into at least one ongoing PM use case implemented within organization. As described below, we asked participants to choose a specific use case for answering questions. Therefore, when a user had no use cases at the moment, we decided to not conduct interview with such a user.

2. Participants Overview

The table contains the overview of 18 users (**u**) that participated in the study. It highlights the user's role with respect to PM (**Role**), region, where user performs PM activities (**PM Activities Location**), PM experience in years (**Years of PM Experience**), the approximate number of different PM projects and/or PM use cases within one project that users have experience with (**PM Projects/Use Cases**), **PM solution** that users are currently using within their organization (if they have an individual experience with many solutions, we ask them to pick one that they currently use), the frequency of the PM solution use (chosen from daily, weekly, monthly, other).

User/Participant Code	Role	PM Activities Location	Years of PM Experience	PM Projects/Use Cases	PM Solution	How often use PM
U1	Project Sponsor	Global	3	>10	Celonis	Daily
U2	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	8	>10	Celonis	Daily
U3	Business Analyst	EU	1	1-5	Celonis	Daily
U4	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	2	5-10	Celonis	Daily
U5	Other: Data Analyst	EU	1	1-5	Disco	Monthly
U6	Business Analyst	EU	1,5	5-10	Celonis	Weekly
U7	Other: Subject Matter Expert	EU	1,5	1-5	Celonis	Daily
U8	Process Excellence Specialist	APAC	5	5-10	Celonis	Monthly
U9	Process Excellence Specialist	EU	2	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U10	Program Manager	Global	1	>10	Celonis	Daily
U11	Process Excellence Specialist	EU	3	5-10	Celonis	Weekly
U12	Business Analyst	EU	4	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U13	Process Excellence Specialist	Global	4	>10	QPR Process Analyzer	Daily
U14	Process Mining Lead	EU	3	>10	Microsoft Process Mining	Daily
U15	Business Engagement Manager	EU	3	1-5	Celonis	Weekly
U16	Process Owner	Global	3	>10	Celonis	Daily
U17	Business Analyst	Global	6 months	>10	Celonis	Daily
U18	Process Team Lead and PM Key User	EU	3	5-10	Celonis	Daily

3. Use Case Selection Criteria

For answering questions, we asked users to choose and focus on their own process mining **use case** implemented within the organization. By use case we refer to the set of analytics in the PM solution, for example, set of dashboards/visuals in the PM solution for analyzing order cancellations in Order-to-Cash process. This way we could get their answers based on a real-life example.

We did not provide any strict requirements for the use case selection. In case a user is involved into multiple use cases, we discussed which one to choose and decided to focus on the one that users use more often. Figures (a) and (b) below provide an overview of business processes and data refresh frequency for chosen use cases.

*For the anonymization purpose, we do not share the detailed information about the use cases, as there are some use cases that we consider rather unique.

4. Interview Details

The interview protocol parts relevant for this study can be found below.

Part I

General Information about Process Mining Experience

3. What is your current role with respect to Process Mining?

- Business Analyst
- Process Excellence Specialist
- Process Owner
- Other

4. Where do you currently conduct your Process Mining activities (please choose the region)?

<https://help.adjust.com/en/article/countries-by-region>

- EMEA - Benelux (Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands)
- EMEA - UK/Ireland
- DACH (Germany, Austria, Switzerland)
- EMEA - Other (not Benelux, not part of DACH, not UK/Ireland)
- Scandinavia (Denmark, Norway, Sweden)
- LATAM (Latin America)
- APAC (Asia-Pacific)
- NA (North America)
- Other

5. How many years of Process Mining Experience do you have?

Feel free to provide approx. number

Enter your answer

6. How many Process Mining Projects/Use cases do you have experience with? (feel free to provide approximate number/range)

Feel free to provide approx. number or range. For example: 5-10

Enter your answer

7. Which Process Mining Solution(s) you have experience with?

If multiple, please select one you currently/recently use

Celonis

Disco

UiPath Process Mining

Microsoft Process Mining

Process Mining by Software AG

Other

8. How often do you use Process Mining solution?

Hourly

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Other

9. Which Process you are currently working on (in Process Mining solution)?

Please select one or multiple options below or specify in Other

Order-to-Cash

Purchase-to-Pay

Plant Maintenance

Other

10. Which Use Case/Analysis you are currently working on (in Process Mining solution)?

Please select one or multiple options below or specify in Other

Time-To-Deliver

Shipped Not Invoiced

On-Time-In-Full

Automation Ratio

Open Invoices

3-way-Match

Other

11. Use Case Focus for the next Questions

The questions in **Part II** and **Part III** are better asked based on a **dashboard/analysis** you are currently using in Process Mining solution.

You are kindly requested to open one of your Process Mining analyses (do not share it, just open it and see for yourself) and use it when answering the questions. If you have multiple dashboards, you are free to choose one (however, the advice is to open the one you use the most **often**).

Share the high-level description of the analysis/use case you have opened:

Enter your answer

12. For how long do you use this use case?

Less than a month

1-6 months

6 months - 1 year

more than 1 year

Other

13. How often do you have a data refresh for this use case?

How often the delta data is uploaded

Daily

Weekly

Monthly

Other

21. Please mark **project phases** for one of the latest developments where you were involved (for example, you were involved into validation sessions)

Project Planning - Process Mining Scope definition

Business Requirements Collection - Use Case definition, which process steps, which KPI's have to be included into the final results

Technical Requirements Collection - Which data sources, data tables, data fields have to be used for the development

Technical Development - Data Source Connection, Data Extraction and Transformation, Model/Dashboards development

Validation Session(s) - Sessions that are dedicated to data checks and logic validation

Enablement Session(s) - Trainings, Specific Enablement Sessions

After-Implementation Use - During Go-Live

Other

23. How would you rate overall interpretability of the view/dashboard you look at (with given interpretability definition)?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel that I understand how to use analysis (PM output) in the PM solution for the selected use case	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that it is simple to use analysis (PM output) in the PM solution for the selected use case	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I can gain insights quite easily out of analysis (PM output) for the selected use case	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

24. If you replied to one or more previous questions (23), can you please share some details why?

Enter your answer

25. Can you please share (some examples) of which insights/tasks do you get out of this dashboard/overview?

Enter your answer

26. Are those insights (from the previous question) immediate or can be achieved only after exploration?

- Yes, immediate
- No, exploration required
- Difficult to answer

27. If possible, please mark during which **phases/activities** (where you were involved) it helped you to gain (some/better) **understanding** on what analysis (PM output) show and how to use/interpret it

- Project Planning** - Process Mining Scope definition
- Business Requirements Collection** - Use Case definition, which process steps, which KPI's have to be included into the final results
- Technical Requirements Collection** - Which data sources, data tables, data fields have to be used for the development
- Technical Development** - Data Source Connection, Data Extraction and Transformation, Model/Dashboards development
- Validation Session(s)** - Sessions that are dedicated to data checks and logic validation
- Enablement Session(s)** - Trainings, Specific Enablement Sessions
- After-Implementation Use** - During Go-Live
- Other

28. Visual Components

Please mark (in the list below), which visuals components are used in the dashboard/overview.

- Process Explorer/Process Map
- Variant Explorer
- Bar chart
- Pie chart
- Donut Chart
- Tabular Forms
- KPIs/Gauges
- Other

29. Did you request (during the overall implementation project) or at any other point in time any adjustments in this dashboard/overview?

Select all that apply

- No
- Yes, during the initial implementation
- Yes, after it went go-live
- Other

30. If you replied to the previous question one of the option with Yes, please answer this question. Otherwise, please skip this question

Change(s) you requested were related to (select all that apply):

- Change Visual Component** - for example, to replace donut chart with bar chart
- Add New Visual Component** - for example, add tabular form or process explorer/map
- General Layout** - reorganize the dashboard/view for more intuitive use
- Update Logic/Formula** - for example, add one more condition into the KPI calculation
- Other

33. Where/How (in which form) did you learn about Process Mining and how to use Process Mining tool?

Select all that apply

- Online Course by Process Mining Vendor
- Offline Course by Process Mining Vendor
- Online Course by Online Course Provider (e.g., Coursera, Udemy, etc)
- Offline Course by [any provider]
- Self-exploration
- University
- Other

